

POLITICAL DISCOURSE AND TRANSLATION

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with some aspects of the translation of texts related to political discourse: textological aspects, metaphorology and translation, precedent phenomena in translation, intertextuality and politically correct vocabulary in translation, etiquette moments. We believe that the translation view can be fruitful for the further development of political linguistics.

Keywords: political discourse, translation, translator

INTRODUCTION

The translator has to master the peculiarities of political discourse in both (all) working languages. The content of political discourse includes all the components (factors) present in the minds of the producer and recipient of the text that can influence the generation and perception of speech: other texts, the political views of the author, the political situation, etc. In bilingual communication with translation, both objective factors associated with overcoming the linguistic and linguo-ethnic divide, and subjective factors associated with the personal characteristics of the translator are added to them. And if even in monolingual communication the personal and social characteristics of the listener and speaker are important then in bilingual communication with translation we have one more listener and speaker (reader and writer), i.e. e. the number of factors that can influence the generation and perception of speech is multiplied.

Comparison of national discourses, in particular political metaphors, provides rich food for thought and further study of contact zones of languages (contact zones) Comparative studies show quantitative and qualitative (frame-slot) discrepancies in the metaphor of languages. However, non-coincidence of metaphorical pictures of the world is far from the only difficulty that a translator faces in real work. In this article, we will consider the objective factors that a translator has to take into account when translating texts of political discourse.

We consider the work of a professional translator, although, in principle, the translation of texts related to the core or periphery of political discourse (from a politician's speech to political jokes) can be relevant in all types of translation - professional, educational and everyday. In the literature devoted to the issues of didactics of translation, educational translation is usually understood as translation as one of the means of learning a foreign language. When training future translators, translation is the goal, while when learning foreign languages, translation is a learning tool. The translation of students-translators in the classroom is also called educational or "professionally oriented"

We will not take into account the situations of educational translation further in the article. Probably, everyone who has a good command of a foreign language has found himself in the situation of everyday translation at least once in his life. These are situations of help to foreigners in their own country or compatriots in a foreign country: in a hotel, shop, on the street, etc.

Professional translation can be official and unofficial. Non-official is understood as a translation carried out by a professional translator in informal situations: conversations in the car, over a cup of coffee or in a bank when exchanging currency.

Situations of everyday and informal translation may coincide. The difference lies in the fact that in the first case a non-professional translates. You can draw an analogy with an amateur football player who plays with friends in the evenings or on weekends, and a professional football player who trains every day and understands the strategy and tactics of the game. A translator may be tasked with performing an official or unofficial translation of a text related to political discourse .

Even with everyday and unofficial translation of such texts, the translator experiences a certain burden of responsibility. Foreigners may ask him to explain why such a tradition exists, what is his personal reaction to the latest news, and so on. This was experienced, in particular, by volunteers and student translators serving the SCO summit held in Yekaterinburg in June 2009.

In such cases, according to K.Rice and H.Fermeer, the translator turns into a specialist in intercultural communications in the broadest sense

. Not without reason, in Soviet times, students-translators were repeated, starting from the first year, again and again: "Motherland begins with a translator!". In a situation where you understand that the border line is coming, if not behind you, then somewhere nearby, sooner or later any practicing interpreter finds himself.

A professional translator encounters texts of political discourse in the following cases of interpretation (IT) and translation (TL):

- interpretation at political negotiations, summits (UP);

- speeches of political leaders (PM);
- informal translation during behind-the-scenes communication (CC);
- (abstractive) translation of foreign-language news, information from websites, creeping line (UP/PP);
- translation of speeches of political leaders for subsequent oral presentation (SP);
- translation and editing of speeches, interviews, transcripts of negotiations for their subsequent publication (and citation) in the mass media (PP);
- translation of materials from bilingual websites and blogs of political leaders (PP);
- translation of memoirs (PP).

More rare situations are also possible: telephone conversations of politicians, translation of a video conference, etc.

In the process, we note that for translators, translation is primarily a process, while for non-translators (translation customers) it is primarily a result, i.e. text .

Let us outline a number of aspects that bring together the interests of political linguistics and translation studies.

1. Textological aspects. Characteristics of texts in the source language (FL), for example, English, and the target language (TL) may not match. For the purposes of translational analysis of the source text (IT) and the text of the translation (PT), I.S. Alekseeva distinguishes 4 types of information: cognitive, operational, emotional and aesthetic.

Cognitive information is facts, proper names and numbers, i.e. "precision information" in the terminology of R.K. Minyar-Belorucheva . In a scientific article, news program or political report, the density of cognitive information is high. Cognitive information is also present in the instructions, although its density per unit of text (for example, per 1000 printed characters) will be lower than in a scientific article or analysis of B. Obama's election promises one year after the election.

Operational information tells the recipient of the text what to do. Usually it is conveyed by imperatives: "check it out", "make sure that", "don't get in - it will kill you!". Obviously, in the instructions for assembling furniture, the density of operational information is higher than in the politician's pre-election speech. Such information is present in slogans, but in a more hidden form: after all, the purpose of any advertisement is to force the buyer to buy this or that product, to vote for this or that party.

Emotional information is carried by words with pronounced connotative meanings, stylistic devices (metaphor, hyperbole, allusions, etc.), often neologisms, in some cases punctuation marks, not quite ordinary text graphics (caricature and caption

to it) , manifestations of subjective modality, deviations from the literary norm, etc. In a politician's election speech, the density of such information is high.

In cases where the form of a text is no less important than its content, we are dealing with aesthetic information. Aesthetic information, expressed non-verbally, we see in music, painting, architecture, dance. In verbal texts, such information is most often contained at the phonetic-graphic level: alliteration and assonance, rhyme and rhythm. A nursery rhyme may look like a Christmas tree or a snowflake. At the lexico-semantic level, one can note semantic , or “speaking”

proper names (Duke of Plunder, musician Trenbregno, village of Viper-no), author's metaphors, neologisms, puns, renewal of phraseological units (“With my dear, paradise and in a hut, if the Volvo is in the garage”).

Aesthetic information is present, first of all, in literary texts. It is present in advertising and political slogans. In passing, we note that it is precisely because of the complex correlation of form and content, verbal and non-verbal, that it is better to refrain from translating song lyrics.

The texts of political discourse in Russian and English are similar to a first approximation. The presence of one or another type of information and the density of information seem to be close. Even in Soviet times, manuals were published on “socio-political” and “newspaper and information” translation .The number of such benefits in post-Soviet times has multiplied many times over.

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